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Youth Restiveness, Militancy & Kidnapping In The Niger Delta, Causes, Effect And Mitigation

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ABSTRACT

Youth restiveness, militancy and kidnapping has fully domicile in the in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. It has become a daily experience in the different states of the Niger Delta. People's movement to their work places, farmland and private businesses are being hampered. It is against this background that this paper seeks to examine the causes, effect, and the possible mitigation to this heinous and obnoxious practices. The paper further examines the theories that laid foundation for the paper and discusses the concept of militancy, youth restiveness and kidnapping. The paper concludes that youth restiveness, kidnapping has actually crippled the economic activities in the entire Niger Delta region, thereby recommends that stiff penalty should be spelt out and implemented by the government to discourage perpetrators of this act of criminality. So as to restore the economic glory of the Oil Rich Niger Delta region of Nigeria.

Keywords: Kidnapping, Youth Restiveness, Militancy

INTRODUCTION

Youth restiveness and militancy in the Niger Delta has taken a new dimension which is now, kidnapping. The kidnapping of all categories of people including older people, and children. Youth restiveness in this region is usually activated when a group of frustrated youths constitute to forcefully demand for their needs.

Niger Delta region of Nigeria is densely populated, it originally consist of Delta, Bayelsa and Rivers State, until the government of former President Olusegun Obasanjo expanded it to include; Abia, Edo, Imo and Ondo State, Oromareghale (2023). Over two (2) million barrels of oil are being extracted from the Niger Delta everyday, yet, Niger Delta states are underdeveloped. The youth lacks employment, quality education, hence they keep wallowing in abject poverty inspite of their oil. Unfortunately, most oil companies operating in the region is not committed to the plight of their host communities. Atojokol (in) the view of SaroWiwa cited in Adekumbi (2018) says that the root causes of conflicts in the Niger Delta region are the inequitable distribution of revenue, and uneven Development among the region and historically youth restiveness has become a transactional device used by Nigerian youths to get what they want from the relevant authority.

In the Niger Delta states (region) the South-south geo-political zones of Nigeria where bulk of the country's oil revenue is obtained, militant youth are reported to be hundreds of thousands in their number within the age bracket of 15 – 46 Okonta & Oronto (2001). Virtually, every state of the Niger Delta, the youth constitute a large percentage of the population and a few of them appear to have access to formal

education while a larger majority do not, hence majority has no formal education, vocational skills necessary to guarantee employment opportunities.

Apart from non acquisition of formal education amongst the large number of the youths, parental neglect and control has also been listed as a contributory factor that lead to youth restiveness.

Ibaba (2015) again, Alojoko (2018) affirmed that most of the parents and guardians are not living up to their expectations in teaching their children morals, norms and values because the norm and values of any society are expected to be in the custody of the different levels of leadership in the society.

In the entire Niger Delta states (region) youths see the leadership to have failed them; they no longer believe in their leaders. Imagine in the Niger Delta, where the resources that sustains the country is coming from, unemployment, hunger becomes a common feature and the youth seems to be worst hit. These are some of the reasons why they felt that government has ignored their plight.

Enweremadu (2018) pointed out that unemployment and suffering among the Niger Delta youth is the main cause of youth restiveness, which manifests into arm robbery, hostility, kidnapping and militancy. It also encourages prostitution, ritual killings and so many form of crime and criminality.

Asuri (2014) assert that there is high population of unemployed, semi-skilled, half educated youth all over Niger Delta, this makes a large number of idle and vulnerable to negative influences. Sometimes, these youths are being recruited by politicians as thugs, paid heavily, armed and also given promises for juicy packages and used for electioneering purposes and after they had won, few of them seem to be remembered by them, they have squandered the money they were given for the job and now back to square one. So, the resultant effects is for them to revolt against their masters (Oga) for neglect. Moreover, the arms that were given to them for the thuggery job had not been retrieved, so these youths will now make use of the arms for their dirty deals; arm robbery, kidnapping and other forms of social vices and unleash mayhem on the innocent citizens dwelling in the Niger Delta states.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework that laid foundation for this paper is;

Frustration-Aggression Theory: Frustration-Aggression theory was propounded by John Dollard and his team of researchers in 1939. The theory was expanded and modified by Leonard Berkowitz and others in 1962. This theory believes that when individuals or groups are denied what they feel they desire legitimately, they feel disappointed which will lead to frustration and violent behavior. The violent behavior will be directed at those they perceive are responsible directly or indirectly for such denial. It also maintains that where expectation does not meet attainment, people tend to confront those they feel are responsible for not attaining the expected issues or benefits. The non-attainment of the expectation leads to anger, frustration and aggressive behavior or violence. This theory is of the opinion that when youths struggles to go through the rigours of training themselves in schools and eventually come out in frying colours hoping they will get a rewarding job at the end of the day but the jobs are nowhere to be found, and six years after graduation are still been forced to departed on parents that struggle to see them through schools, some might get frustrated and decided to be involved in any crime just to make end meet.

MILITANCY

Militants are group of cultists, kidnapers, assassins, terrorizing the entire Niger Delta region with the false intention of chasing the foreigners who are exploring crude oil in the region. But the facts remains that they do about kidnapping people for ransom. Their activities have brought fear, inflict pains to families and innocent individuals resident in the Niger Delta region. This set of criminals and thugs operate mostly in the creek, they usually come out of the creek to kidnap their victims and take them into the creek and demand for ransom.

THE CONCEPT OF KIDNAPPING

The concept kidnapping seems to have begun around 1682 among those who carry out this crime. American Heritage Dictionary of English language stated that the two words 'kid' and 'napper' were slangs the criminals used. Kid which still has an informal meaning little or joke; 'napper' is obsolete slang for a thief, coming from the verb nap, to steal. In 1678, the year the word was first record, kidnappers piled their trade to secure laborers for plantations in colonies in North America (Ehinddero, 2010). Kidnapping is a crime of unlawful, forceful seizure and detention of a person or persons against his/her or their wish, in anticipation of payment of ransom or to settle some scores of disagreement (Linus, 2015). It is restriction to someone else liberty which is a violation to the provision of freedom of movement as enshrined in the constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria (Okonkwo, 1980).

For this reason, Siegel (1986) sees kidnapping by nature is as an acquisitive crime which is an offense against the value system of a society. Kidnapping is broadly inclusive in assault. He construed the nature of kidnapping in his comments as involving: Any person who unlawfully imprison, and the take him out of Nigeria, without his consent, or unlawfully imprison any person within Nigeria in such a manner as a to prevent him from applying to a court for his release or from discovering to any other person the place where he is imprisoned, or in such a manner as to prevent

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Ugwu (2010) avowed that, there is a dehumanizing tendency involved in the crime of kidnapping as it often leads to the death of the victim. The view of Ugwu is essentially true because kidnapping crime is carried out in our country, the issue is usually beyond ransom taking because death is usually a resultant consequence, for those who cannot or whose people could not meet up with the often exorbitant amount called out for as ransom after a disgracing bargain or negotiation.

The Causes of Kidnapping: Ohakhire (2010) clarified that kidnapping is associated with quest for ransom, revenge and ritual. That is the dictum of kidnapping '3rs' of kidnapping. Other researchers have also campaigned for the following reasons to be responsible for Kidnapping.

1. Challenge of Poverty: Poverty is a global phenomenon which is a recurring problem in Nigeria. It is evident from personal observation, scholarly works, newspaper, radio and television that despite its abundant resources and oil wealth" Nigeria Niger delta ravaged by poverty. The situation has worsened since the late 1990's to the extent that the country is considered one of the poorest countries in the world; over seventy percent of the population is classified as poor and most underdeveloped par of Nigeria living in abject poverty (Rural Poverty Portal (2008). Kinoti (1994) in Olulowo (2017) posited that poverty is directly related to crime. He contends that if people do not have enough to eat, they steal to survive". When people become desperate for food and other necessities they will steal and even kill to get what they need. The 2004 Human Development Indicators put Nigeria as number 151 out of 177 countries. Poverty in Nigeria is generally believed to be prime cause of kidnapping in the country. Justifying this, Garland (2002) posits that virtually, all the various theories of crime causation have explanatory value; it is therefore axiomatic that poverty and social deprivation would in varying degrees, adjusting for intervening variables predispose people to criminality. Most of the kidnappers are lured by poverty; poverty frustrates them into harsh and uncivilized thought and "" actions.

2. Challenge of Unemployment: Lack of employment opportunities for the youths in different parts of Niger Delta is one major cause of prevalence of kidnapping. Inyang (2009) associated kidnapping to the endemic rate of youth joblessness. He corroborated this fact by citing the widely acknowledged adage, which says that "an idle man. is the devil's workshop" to present the situation of unemployment in

Nigeria. Linus (2015) noted that there are uncountable able-bodied men and women in Nigeria roaming the streets of Port Harcourt, Bayelsa, Warri etc in search of non-existing job. Out of frustration together with mounting responsibilities to tackle many idle young persons have ventured into criminal activities of which kidnapping are not an exemption. A graduate who is unable to secure a job is psychologically bereft of other means of survival. Such. The existence of vast reservoir of unemployed youths and underground republic in the country. It is called the republic of hoodlums, a reservoir of almost limitless supply of hungry, angry, willing and able fighters for murky causes. It is from this army that the various ethnic militias and kidnapers are drawing their cadre (Amuta, 2001).

3. Proliferation of Arms and Military Uniforms: Inyang (2009) in Ilechukwu Leonard Chidi, Uchem Rose and Asogwa Uche (2015) believed that the purchase of large number of arms as a result of political patronage of miscreant who were dumped after elections may indirectly encourage and enhance kidnapping. He equated today's kidnapping situation to the bane of arm robbery in the early eighties where many young-able bodied men who fought during the Nigerian civil war were discharged and sent home with nothing. Meanwhile since the schools they left behind were destroyed and there were no jobs to engage them and keep them busy. Many of them consequently took to armed robbery, since as ex-soldiers they were armed with weapons, having acquired the skill and guns during the war. The story is almost the same today as politicians employ most idle youths as political thugs and later dumped them after elections. Therefore, the youths (thugs) who have been abandoned by their master after winning elections are now busy kidnapping innocent person and relative of those persons they surged to be wealthy (Inyang and Ubong, 2013).

4. Policy of Cashless Economy; Some are of the opinion that, the prevalence of kidnapping is no unconnected with the recent cashless economy that had reduced the possibility of pilfering huge amount of cash. They added that the armed robbers then transform into kidnapping. Those robbers see kidnapping as being more lucrative than stealing (Linus, 2015).

5. Moral Decadence and Quest to Get Rich Quick Syndrome

The challenge of moral decadence and the quest to get rich syndrome are some of causative factors of kidnapping according to Inyang and Ubong (2013). Inyang (2009) again established these in his proposition that in Nigeria, nobody asks questions on how people make their wealth. He contended that a poor person today/ can show up with an expensive car tomorrow and nobody dare to question the sudden wealth. He further asserted that people who have donated money to develop their communities are rewarded with chieftaincy titles thereby creating a wrong impression in the minds of Nigerian youth who thereafter take to kidnapping. Inyang and Ubong (2013) identified greed as one of causes of kidnapping in Nigeria. They averred that, greed has caused many persons to take part in heinous criminal acts. Kidnapping is perhaps one crime that promotes greed and despair on the human person. For many, it is greed that pushes perpetrators to brutalize and torture a stranger and put his family through a cruel ordeal for weeks, months sometimes years.

6. Corruption and Poor Governance: The economic failure is attributed to wearing down of the state's institutional and administrative capacities, corruption pandemic, inconsistency in economic/policy, external shocks, poor state of the rule of law and military dictatorship, rising ethnic nationality conflicts and the state's inability to implement its policies and decisions due to corruption arid refraction of such policies through prism of ethnic and sectional interest provoked some other sections to criminality especially that of kidnapping (Arewa, 2013). This is called the breakdown of institutional infrastructures (Fukuyama, 2004). The foundations of institutional framework in Nigeria are very insecure and have motivated a weakening of state governance and democratic accountability, thus, paralyzing the existing formal and legitimate rules nested in the hierarchy of social order (Achumba, *et al*, 20.13) The state of insecurity in the Niger Delta is a function of government failure. This manifests in the incapacity of government to deliver public goods to its citizens (Igbuzor, 2011). This lack of basic necessities by the Niger Delta has created a growing army of frustrated people who resort to violence at the slightest provocation or opportunity. Even though, Niger Delta full of resources to meet the needs of her people,

the well-established culture of corruption in public service has brought about the drought of basic necessities.

7. The Use of Hard Drag

The increase of kidnapping is connected to high use and trafficking of hard drugs (Okoli, 2009). The use of hard drugs no doubt leads to violent crimes such as kidnapping and armed robbery within the country. Several drug sale points are emerging everyday where criminal activities are planned, perfected and executed. Some streets in the state have been turned into no-go areas for law abiding residents as unscrupulous miscreants have turned them into ghettos and hideouts for their hard drugs operation. After taking the drugs, the takers became high, fearless, bold and inhuman and they can perpetrate kidnapping under this state of mind without qualms of conscience.

8. Inequality and Absence of Fairness and Justice

The perception of marginalization by many Nigerians is informed by the ostentation showed by the Political class and elite vis-a-vis the grinding poverty to which citizens was subjected to. Even security has been bourgeoisified by the elite. As Egwu (2000) contends, the security of the Nigerian nation-state has been reduced to that of the ruler and his immediate supporters, thus, the security calculus of the Nigerian state has failed because it does not include vital aspects of social and national development supported by the provision of basic social, economic or even military conditions necessary for effective national security. This state of inequality, unfairness and injustice has toughened the people, forcing them to take their destiny into their hands.

The Consequences of Kidnapping

Economic Effect of Kidnapping: Inyang and Ubong (2013) in Ilechukwu (2015) averred that the economic effects of kidnapping include direct and indirect costs. Direct Cost of Kidnapping involves the economic value that individuals and government may be lost to kidnappers, much money has been paid as ransom. Former Inspector of Police, Sir Mike Okiro, reported that N15 billion have been paid as ransom to the kidnappers between 2006 and 2009 (Kyrian, 2009). Inyang and Ubong (2013) posited out that in many cases, it is often the bread winners of families that are usually targeted, the implication is always felt particularly within the family, whereby members of such, families will have to feed themselves and adjust to their; normal daily activities, until they secure the release of the victim. If the victim is a businessman or woman the business will suffer, if he is a civil servant or an artisan, his place of work will be affected adversely. In both cases there is going to be some setback. Indirect Cost of Kidnapping includes expenditure on preventive measures, such as the employment of private security personnel. At government level, the economic effects include the expenditure on security and security agencies (Inyang and Ubong, 2013).

Political effects of kidnapping:

1. Elective and Political Violence: There can be increase in the use of political thugs of strong politicians to threaten their political opponents, thereby derailing the democratic process (Thom-Otuya, 2010)
2. According to Thom-Outya (201) the alarming rate of kidnapping activities in the country could overturn democracy and pave way for military invasion into politics and send the politicians parking. If political gladiators will use kidnapping, as established crime in Nigeria to intimidate their opponent, then, they will be prompting military storming into Nigeria politics to remedy the insecurity of lives, properties and business with military dispatch. This according to (Otuya, 2010) will lead to the utmost backwardness of Nigeria society.
3. Kidnapping activities shoot up the abundance of arms. The business requires good firing power i.e firearms in order to kidnap the targeted victims, to scare people out of the sight and to resist the law enforcement agents. Politicians equip the thugs with arms to use in threatening their opponents.
4. The inability of the security agencies to stop kidnapping occurrences in the country exposes the weakness of the security agencies in the country.

Social Effects of Kidnapping

1. Kidnapping affects the social life and social relation of many people who are held hostages in their homes from dusk to dawn, for fear of being kidnapped (Inyang and Ubong 2013). As a result of kidnapping, night travel has become a high risk. Furthermore, many people have been forced out of their newly completed houses by kidnappers. People are compelled to present an unfinished look of poverty by not painting the external walls of their houses. Many people are afraid to buy or use new motor vehicles for the fear of kidnappers. Soyombo (2009), attests that rich people have resorted to riding in taxi cab and commercial motorcycle popularly called Okada to markets, schools, offices and social outings as a means of check hostage takers.
2. The incident of kidnapping in the era of democracy in Nigeria dents the ' image of the nation in the global scene (Ilechuckwu et al. 2015). Thom-Otuya (2010) observed that in the game of international relations, the image and prestige of a country is very important to her interest. If Nigeria that ought to attract foreign investors has a very poor and dented image, she will probably find it difficult making friends and attracting foreign ; investors. The truth of the matter is exposed by Odey (2001) when he noted ' that every whore in the world; Nigerians are generally feared like dogs, dreaded like criminals, cautiously approached like snakes and avoided as a leper.

Psychological/Emotional Effects

Kidnapping creates physical and psychological fear of insecurity among the Nigerians. This makes contractors to abandon their project due to fear of being kidnapped. This trend retards growth and development. For instance, oil workers abandoned their job for their safety, at the detriment to oil production which is the main source of our economy. Nigeria earns over 90% of foreign exchange from oil and gas production as result of kidnapping, it translates to great threat to the National security and challenges to the government and law enforcement agency. Fear of insecurity could lead to migration of foreign investors to other countries. Consequently this creates capital flight from the state thereby affecting the economy of lie nation. Companies can be closed making some people jobless. This could create threat to security of the nation (Ilechuckwu et al. 20 f 5).

Moral Effects of Kidnapping

1. Some victims of the kidnappers could be sexually abused in the process of their captors await the demanded payment (Ilechuckwu et al. 2015).
2. Some victims of the kidnappers have lost their lives in the hands of their abductors. For Instance: Dr. Gabriel Olowoyo, the Attah of Aiyede Orisagbeni died in motor accident when he was being transported by the kidnappers; He. nrian Omovegie was kidnapped and killed in Delta state; Mrs. Owoidighe Ekpoattai and two policemen died in the hand of their abductors among many others. Life is sacred, but kidnappers have made human life to lose its value Their immoral acts have reduced, man into semblance of animals. They have made man to lose his freedom and dignity (Ilechuckwu et al. 2015).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper concludes and affirmed the existence of kidnappers has become a thorn in the flesh of many citizens and foreigners domicile in Ogun state South West Nigeria. Kidnapping is growing at an extraordinary rate across the State. People's movements to their working places have been hampered by the fear of kidnappers.

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